

A Study of Student Perceptions of Ethical Values at University Level

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Abstract

This descriptive study was designed to explore student perceptions of ethical values at university level. The purpose of this study to identify the perceptions of student regarding ethical values. The main objective of this study was to investigate the ethical values of students, the importance of in their lives and how they are applying in daily different aspects of life. Data was collected through a survey questionnaire adopted from the research work were selected through sample random sampling technique. For this purpose, surveys were conducted to collect the data from 500 university students of both public and private sectors. The collect data was analyzed by using statistical package for Social Science (SPSS). It was concluded that students give more importance to ethical values in different aspects of life.

Key Words: Ethical values, students, university, perceptions

1. Introduction

Accordingly, a valuable thing is the one that is important, worthy or useful. Therefore, values are fundamental in our life and lie behind the all choices we make. There are many values govern the choices we make in our life, however lots of them have nothing to do with morality. Economic values for instance, are the ones lie behind the all

choices we make in economy and have nothing to do with morality per ethical values are the ones we make ethical choices based on them, or they are the kind of values that have to do with being good or doing the right thing. There are many ethical values. Justice, honesty, empathy, compassion, respect and responsibility are the most important ones (Halstead and Taylor 2000).

Morals allude to arrangement of guidelines that portrays adequate direct in the public eye. Morals fill in as a manual for moral day by day living and causes us judge whether our conduct can be advocated. Morals alludes to society's feeling of the correct method for living our everyday lives. It does this by setting up standards, standards, and qualities on which we can base our direct. The ideas most specific profession connected with morals are truth, genuineness, reasonableness, and value. While a moral is a societal concern, it is of basic significance to the professions that serve society. Since experts, for example, doctors, lawyers, architects, and property and office supervisors give benefits that influence our welfare; they create proficient codes of morals that set up proficient guidelines for conduct (Bell, 2008).

Qualities are characterized as the demonstrations, traditions, and establishments that a gathering of individuals respect positively. Proclamations of significant worth commonly contain

expressions of endorsement, objection, and commitment. A portion of these words may be great, awful, should, and ought not. Be that as it may, esteem judgments don't need to contain particular esteem words. "That is a lie" does not contain a specific expression of objection, but rather the suggestion that a lie isn't right is comprehended (Avolio, 2005).

In the meantime, honesty, responsibility and duty in directing scholarly research shape the foundation of any scholastic undertaking and infringement of broadly perceived scholarly research norms speak to genuine offenses to the whole scholarly network at the Institute and are viewed as damaging for its believability and expert as organization that advances brilliance in scholarly research in Europe.

Intellectuals all through history have again and again given answer. Their message is amazingly clear and may be consolidated as "the nonappearance of usage of good characteristics". Since the specific start of human progress moral conduct has been a need for various scholars, teachers, and masterminds, who educated and imparted their thoughts and encounters to followers, social orders, government officials, and other individuals.

Distinctive makers and teachers trust that morals and good characteristics getting ready and change the commitment of the family and religious foundations; along these lines, this may speak to the thoughts that impact people to feel that ethical characteristics require not be told in schools. Fisher (2003) clarified when he attested that a surface way to deal with morals, which is related with self-intrigue, won't advance moral conduct. Be that as it may, a profound approach, roused by the longing to make the best choice has the possibility to do as such.

The teacher plays important role in molding and shaping the ethical values and good manners of the student's. A teacher plays his role towards in two ways. First, inside the

school by preparing students for effective citizens, and second, outside the students by assuming the role of social work and agent of social work

A teacher can present the values of society in a dignified manner for the betterment of the students in the society. The students are following the ethical values or not. The university students apply ethical values in their lives or not. The parents told them about their ethical values or not and whether they are applying them in their lives. The students give respect to their teachers. Students adopt honesty or cheating in every classroom work. The purpose of this study is to identify a study of student perceptions of ethical values at university level. The study focused on three research objectives; To find out which ethical values university students consider useful in different aspects of life. To investigate which ethical values university students apply in different aspects of life. To identify the relation between ethical values considered important and applied in different aspects of life.

2. Material and Methods

The samples of this research were the students enrolled in B.S (HONS) programs of 4 conveniently selected universities from the District Lahore. Two universities were public and two universities were private selected for sample size. In Lahore district the Public universities were Lahore College for Women University, University of Punjab selected. In Lahore District the Private universities were University of Management & Technology, Minhaj-ul-Quran University, selected. In this selected universities the students were selected conveniently in the class B.S (HONS). Researcher takes 250 students from public and 250 from private universities which consists department of Education and Chemistry from Semesters number 1,2,7,8. The sample of this research was 500 students.

The researcher has done the quantitative research by following the survey research design. The researcher collected the data visiting the institute of education and research in university of the Punjab Lahore. For the collection of data, the researcher personally visited in all these selected universities of both Public and Private in Lahore District. The researcher selected 500 students as sample from each of the mentioned universities from Public and Private sectors in Lahore District. The researcher selected students were randomly from each university. The researcher constructed questionnaire based upon the Ethical Values and each Ethical Values based upon the Importance and apply and allowed this numbers from importance and apply (1, to 10) The validity of the questionnaire was checked by the qualified person from L.C.W.U. the quantitative data was collected through 500 questionnaires which were statistically analyzed using SPSS-23.

3. Results and Discussion

We enrolled 500 students in our study of BS (Hons.) level from four public and private sectors universities (Lahore College for Women University Lahore, Punjab University Lahore, University of Management and Technology and MINHAJ University Lahore) of various semesters.

Table 1 indicates the number of male respondents is higher in private universities as compared to the number of male respondents in public universities. Similarly the number of female respondents is higher in public universities as compared to the number of female respondents in private universities. Table 1 also showed that the highest number of respondents were from chemistry department. The results about father education, mother education and annual family income were also given in Table-1.

The analysis indicates that students are highly satisfied with role of universities for a study of student perceptions of ethical values. Results revealed that student perceptions of ethical values are highly satisfied. Most of the students were agreed that they consider ethical values are important while raise the achievements. Most of the students had built positive relationship with each other to opt rewards or recognition based on their ethical values.

Ethical values are many and very diverse because they are linked with life, with us, students and professionals or simply individuals.

The requirement for illuminating how such joining may and ought to happen has incited a wide range of understandings and differences by advanced education and neighborhood level instruction experts. The inquiry still remained how ethical values may apply to instruction with a specific end goal to achieve positive and compelling outcomes for the individual, families, and society. Ethical values are perceived as profitable however are not constantly connected in the correct way into life (Conroy, 2000; DeRoche& Williams, 2001; Devettere, 2002; Oksenberg, 1993; Springer, 2000; Wilson, 1993). The present investigation happy with the past examination enhances that ethical values are perceived as significant yet are not constantly connected in the best possible way into life students gives more importance in ethical qualities yet connected not exactly.

The longing for coordinating moral qualities into training as a component of the educational module has been talked about in a wide range of courses and inside assortment of professions (Homann, 1996). The present examination additionally demonstrates that distinctive students have diverse recognitions and distinctive routes how to apply and how to give more importance.

Trustworthiness was the most noteworthy positioned incentive among staff and director members with a mean of 6.88 taken after by just and receptive with methods for 6.63. Open foundations of advanced education put extraordinary accentuation on the right to speak freely and request and urge students to effectively take interest in inquire about exercises (Cummings, 2001; Halstead, 2000; Huitt, 2002). Subsequently, The present investigation likewise enhance that the genuineness takes most astounding significance in ethical values and students urge to take part with each other and 99 % students are consent to gives Importance. The connection amongst instruction and morals, and in addition the critical need to blend training with ethical values and relate them with all regions of learning, spaces of society, work, and life has verifiably had conflicting inclinations, distinctive criteria and different understanding (Kagan, 2001).The present examination enhance that the need of ethical values in understudy point

of view are most noteworthy and the association with values takes significance. The requirement for illuminating how such joining may and ought to happen has incited a wide range of understandings and differences by advanced education and neighborhood level instruction experts. The inquiry still remained how Ethical values may apply to instruction with a specific end goal to achieve positive and compelling outcomes for the individual, families, and society. Moral qualities are perceived as profitable however are not constantly connected in the correct way into life (Conroy, 2000; DeRoche& Williams, 2001; Devettere, 2002).The present investigation happy with the past examination enhances that ethical values are perceived as significant yet are not constantly connected in the best possible way into life students gives more importance in ethical values but less applied of ethical values.

Table-1: Results of demographic variables

Variables		Universities		
		Public	Private	Total
Gender	Male	83(33.2%)	165(66%)	248(49.6%)
	Female	167(66.8%)	85(34%)	252(50.4%)
Department	Education	122(48.8%)	122(48.8%)	244(48.8%)
	Chemistry	128(51.2%)	128(51.2%)	256(51.2%)
Father education	Under Matric	7(2.8%)	15(6.0%)	22(4.4%)
	Matric	71(28.4%)	46(18.4%)	117(23.4%)
	Intermediate	78(31.2%)	96(38.4%)	174(34.8%)
	Graduate	63(25.2%)	77(30.8%)	140(28.0%)
	Master/MPhil and above	31(12.4%)	16(6.4%)	47(9.4%)
Mother education	Under Matric	89(35.6%)	45(18.0%)	134(26.8%)
	Matric	110(44.0%)	71(28.4%)	181(36.2%)
	Intermediate	27(10.8%)	61(24.4%)	88(17.6%)
	Graduate	11(4.4%)	41(16.4%)	52(10.4%)
	Master/MPhil and above	13(5.2%)	32(12.8%)	45(9.0%)

Annual family income	12 lac	82(32.8%)	75(30.0%)	157(31.4%)
	13 or 24 lac	114(45.6%)	121(48.4%)	235(47.0%)
	25 lac or above	54(21.6%)	54(21.6%)	108(21.6%)

Table-2 Highest and lowest means considered importance by public sector and private sector

Ethical values (importance)	Public	Mean	SD	Private	Mean	SD
Highest						
Respect	Public	8.81	2.29	Private	9.22	1.77
Honesty	Public	8.74	2.20	Private	8.88	2.05
Responsibility	Public	8.72	2.16	Private	9.05	1.75
Knowledge	Public	8.52	2.19	Private	8.92	1.85
Kindness	Public	8.69	2.03	Private	8.82	1.91
Patience	Private	8.87	1.87	Public	8.45	2.34
Lowest						
Detachment	Public	7.43	2.67	Private	7.58	2.46
Perseverance	Public	7.91	2.10	Private	8.07	2.09
Comprehension	Public	7.97	2.02	Private	8.13	2.10
Initiative	Public	7.97	2.16	Private	8.25	2.06
Analysis	Public	8.12	2.05	Private	8.36	1.98
Humility	Private	8.22	2.38	Public	8.16	2.25

Table-3: Highest and lowest means considered apply by public sector and private sector

Ethical values (apply)	Public	Mean	SD	Private	Mean	SD
Highest						
Respect	Public	7.72	2.35	Private	7.88	2.14
Kindness	Public	7.69	2.23	Private	7.85	2.07
Love	Public	7.48	2.73	Private	7.96	2.55
Fairness	Public	7.34	2.32	Private	7.46	2.16
Good humor	Public	7.24	2.29	Private	7.48	2.10
Lowest						
Detachment	Public	6.18	2.68	Private	6.38	2.35
Tolerance	Public	6.49	2.59	Private	6.83	2.31
Initiative	Public	6.70	2.27	Private	6.96	1.94
Patience	Public	6.68	2.55	Private	7.10	2.26
Perseverance	Public	6.71	2.12	Private	7.04	1.92
Comprehension	Private	6.72	1.96	Public	6.90	1.98
Self-contentment	Private	6.96	1.86	Public	6.95	2.14

4. Conclusion

This study was conducted in order to identify a study of student perceptions of ethical values at university level in public and private sector of Lahore city, as little research has been conducted in this field. A thorough and detailed literature review was conducted relating to the definitions of ethical values as a concept and the journey from its beginning to the current stage. As a result of this practice, questionnaires are constructed that shows the effect ethical values.

The results of the data analysis, which was conducted in order to identify a study of student perceptions of ethical values at university level in public and private sector of Lahore city. It was concluded that had a positive response for student perceptions about ethical values. The students give more importance of ethical values in different aspects of life, but less applied of ethical values in different aspect of life

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